

Assessing Institutional Capacity and Policy Gaps for Effective Flood Mitigation Strategies in Urban Communities of Northeast Nigeria

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Abstract

Urban flooding has remained one of the most persistent and damaging climate-related hazards in Northeast Nigeria, where rapid urbanization, weak infrastructure, and institutional fragility converge with increasing climate variability. This study thus assessed the Institutional Capacity and Policy Gaps needed for Effective Flood Mitigation Strategies and Resilience in selected Urban Communities of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States (BAY States in Northeast Nigeria). Using a descriptive research design integrated with quantitative household surveys and inferential statistical analysis, data were collected from 650 respondents across the study area, representing diverse socioeconomic and ecological contexts. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze perceptions of structural and non-structural flood risk measures, while chi-square tests examined the relationship between mitigation strategies, institutional capacity, and urban resilience outcomes. Findings indicate that while basic structural measures such as drainage channels and embankments exist, their effectiveness were constrained by poor maintenance, inadequate funding, and weak enforcement of land-use regulations. Non-structural measures, including public awareness campaigns and early warning systems, were more visible but unevenly implemented. Institutional analysis revealed limited technical capacity, fragmented coordination among disaster management agencies, and insufficient integration of community actors, particularly youth into flood governance processes, hence the need for enhanced flood mitigation strategies and institutional capacity to achieve community resilience. The study concludes that urban flood risk management in Northeast Nigeria remains largely reactive and fragmented. It thus recommends the strengthening of institutional frameworks, consistent policy enforcement, adequate financing, and inclusive, sustainable flood resilience, and community-driven approaches that integrate both structural and non-structural measures.

Keywords: *Flood mitigation, institutional capacity, disaster governance, urban planning, Northeast Nigeria.*

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Introduction

Flood mitigation has become a central concern in climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions of developing countries. Globally, flood losses have increased significantly over the past two decades, reflecting both climate-induced changes in precipitation patterns and the expansion of vulnerable urban settlements (IPCC, 2023; UNDRR, 2022). While mitigation strategies aim to reduce exposure and vulnerability, their effectiveness is strongly influenced by institutional capacity, governance quality, and policy coherence.

In Nigeria, recurrent flooding has exposed systemic weaknesses in urban planning, infrastructure provision, and disaster governance. The northeastern states of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe are especially vulnerable due to ecological fragility, limited infrastructure, and the prolonged effects of insecurity and displacement. Although government agencies such as the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), State Emergency Management Agencies (SEMAs), and local authorities are mandated to manage flood risks, urban flooding continues to cause widespread damage annually. This raises critical questions about the adequacy, coordination, and sustainability of existing mitigation strategies.

Flooding is predominantly urban/flash floods which are caused by intense rainfall, inadequate drainage infrastructure, and blocked waterways (Ibrahim et al., 2016). Yola (Adamawa State), with Coordinates: Latitude 9.2333°N, Longitude 12.4667°E, is the capital of Adamawa State, is located on the Benue River floodplain, comprising Yola North and Yola South LGAs. Its low-lying topography makes it highly susceptible to riverine floods, especially during heavy rainfall and releases from the Lagdo Dam in Cameroon (Ati et al., 2010). Major floods (e.g., 2012 and 2022) displaced thousands of residents and devastated infrastructure, transport, and agriculture (Adebayo and Tukur, 2018; Ologunorisa, 2014). While, Potiskum (Yobe State), with Coordinates: Latitude 11.7167°N, Longitude 11.0833°E, is the largest urban and commercial center in Yobe State, located along major transport routes linking northern Nigeria with central and southern regions. It is famous for hosting Nigeria's largest cattle market (Audu, 2013).

Despite the presence of flood mitigation measures, urban communities in Northeast Nigeria continue to experience severe flood impacts. Drainage systems are frequently blocked or poorly maintained, land-use regulations are weakly enforced, and flood control projects often lack community ownership. Institutional overlap and unclear mandates further undermine effective flood risk management. These persistent challenges suggest that the problem extends beyond hazard exposure to include governance, institutional, and policy failures that require systematic investigation.

Conceptual Clarifications and Review of Literature

Flood Mitigation Strategies

The harsh reality of flooding causing untold hardship for millions across the flood-prone regions all over the world cannot be overemphasized. The issue of critical concern is how to mitigate the menace associated with flood. In other words, Flood mitigation is a combination of smart planning, innovative engineering, and community action that offers hope in reducing the devastating impacts of floods before disaster strikes. Modern flood management recognizes that the most effective strategies combine both structural and non-structural measures. While structural solutions provide tangible protection, they can sometimes create a false sense of security (Chan et al., 2017, 2020). A levee might protect against a 100-year flood, but what happens when a 500-year flood occurs? Non-

structural measures fill these gaps by ensuring communities remain prepared even when physical defenses fail.

Research shows that implementing non-structural measures is often more cost-effective than structural ones. The United States Federal Emergency Management Agency estimates that for every dollar spent on mitigation, communities save approximately four dollars in future disaster costs. This remarkable return on investment makes non-structural approaches increasingly attractive to cash-strapped governments worldwide (Jamrussri & Toda, 2017; Mohita & Sellub, 2013). Flood mitigation strategies are broadly categorized into structural measures, such as drainage construction, embankments, and flood barriers, and non-structural measures, including land-use planning, early warning systems, and public awareness campaigns (Adelekan, 2021). While structural measures offer immediate protection, non-structural approaches are increasingly emphasized for their cost-effectiveness and sustainability.

Policy and Urban Planning Dimensions

Urban planning plays a critical role in flood mitigation through zoning regulations, enforcement of building codes, and protection of natural drainage channels. In Nigeria, policy implementation gaps and political interference have been identified as major obstacles to sustainable urban flood management (Salihu, 2018). Capacity building for youth in climate action encompasses a wide range of activities, from formal education and training programs to informal skill-sharing networks and mentorship schemes. In Nigeria, there has been a growing recognition of the need to equip young people with the knowledge and skills necessary to address climate challenges effectively (Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2022).

One of the primary avenues for capacity building is through the formal education system. In recent years, there has been a push to integrate climate change education into Nigeria's national curriculum. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) has been working on developing a comprehensive climate change curriculum for primary and secondary schools. This initiative aims to ensure that young Nigerians are educated about climate change from an early age, fostering a generation of climate-conscious citizens (NERDC, 2022).

Institutional Capacity and Disaster Governance

Institutional capacity refers to the ability of organizations to effectively plan, implement, and coordinate disaster risk reduction activities. Studies indicate that weak institutional frameworks, limited funding, and poor coordination often undermine flood mitigation efforts in developing countries (UNDP, 2019; World Bank, 2021). Effective disaster governance requires clear roles, stakeholder collaboration, and integration of risk reduction into development planning.

Developing countries are especially vulnerable to such disasters but are often the least capable of coping with the associated impacts because of their limited adaptive capacity. Despite the increased interest in strengthening institutional capacity, it remains a challenge for many developing countries. Institutional capacity for disaster management and risk reduction can be built through various mechanisms. One key approach is via the agriculture sector, where climate-resilient agriculture has become an effective tool for adapting to climate change and developing resilience in the long run – resulting in increased capacity for disaster management and risk reduction at the system, institutional, and individual levels (UNDP, 2016; Babu, et al 2019).

Institutional Capacity Gaps and Capacity-Building Strategies in Fragile Urban Contexts

Institutional capacity gaps in flood disaster management in fragile urban contexts of Northeast Nigeria manifest as chronic under-resourcing, fragmented coordination, limited technical expertise, and weak linkages between federal, state, and local levels. In the BAY States, State Emergency Management Agencies (SEMAs) and Local Emergency Committees often lack trained personnel,

equipment, and funding to maintain drainage systems, embankments, or early warning infrastructure, resulting in reactive rather than preventive responses (Nextier SPD, 2022; Kuranga et al., 2023). Conflict further erodes capacity by restricting staff mobility, damaging facilities, and diverting resources to security priorities.

Capacity-building strategies must therefore be multi-pronged: technical training (e.g., flood modeling, GIS), institutional strengthening (e.g., clearer roles via NDMF updates), and community linkages (e.g., participatory risk mapping). Recent initiatives (e.g., IOM's 2025–2028 Crisis Response Plan) emphasize localized training and resource allocation in BAY States. Your study's evidence of moderate intervention effectiveness and persistent gaps (e.g., poor maintenance) highlights the urgency of sustained, context-sensitive capacity building to enhance resilience in fragile urban settings.

Materials & Methods

The Study Area

The area covered in the study was selected urban communities of Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe States (BAY States) in Northeast Nigeria. These states lie within the semiarid and savannah ecological zones, characterized by highly variable rainfall, prolonged dry seasons, and increasing vulnerability to climate-related disasters such as floods and droughts (Abaje *et al.*, 2015; Umar *et al.*, 2020). The chosen study sites Maiduguri (Borno State), Yola (Adamawa State), and Potiskum (Yobe State) reflect different ecological, socioeconomic, and hydrological settings, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of flood risk in the region. Maiduguri (Borno State) with Coordinates: Latitude 11.8333°N, Longitude 13.1500°E, is the capital and largest city of Borno State, lies within the Sudan savannah ecological zone and is drained by the seasonal Ngadda River, which flows into the Alau Dam. Rapid urbanization, population growth, and influx of internally displaced persons (IDPs) have intensified land-use pressures (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2017). Flooding here is seasonal, driven by heavy rainfall, inadequate drainage, and encroachment on natural waterways (Aliyu and Amadu, 2017). Floods disrupt markets, housing, and transport systems, affecting traders, farmers, and urban livelihoods. See Figure 1 for the study location.

Figure 1. Nigeria Showing the 3 States and LGAs in the Study Area

Source: UNHCR, (2025)

Materials and Methods

With the aim of this to assess the nature, impacts, and mitigation strategies of flood-based disasters within the BAY states, it adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study population was limited to the residents of Maiduguri in Borno State with urban population of 1,097,600 (CityPopulation.de, 2025), Yola in Adamawa State with urban population of over 610,400 people (CityPopulation.de, 2025), and that of Potiskum, located in Yobe State with a population of 322,100 (CityPopulation.de, 2025), which gave total population of 2,030,100. With the aid of Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 688 was determined and out of this number, 650 (94.5%) copies of the questionnaire administered were properly filled and retrieved. The questionnaire instrument was administered on persons chosen by the inclusive criteria of study. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for data presentation and analysis, while Cross tabulations and chi-square tests were used to assess associations between household vulnerability characteristics and flood exposure.

Results and Discussions

Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate by State

Table 1 shows the questionnaire distribution and response rate by state. The response rate across the BAY States was consistently high, averaging 94.5% overall, with Borno (94.6%), Adamawa (94.2%), and Yobe (94.5%) all exceeding the widely accepted 70% benchmark for survey studies (Creswell, 2014). This high return rate enhances the reliability and validity of the findings, ensuring that the study adequately represents urban communities in the three states.

Table 1. Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate by State

State / Location	Distributed	Returned	Not Returned	Response Rate (%)
Borno (Maiduguri)	372	352	20	94.6
Adamawa (Yola)	207	195	12	94.2
Yobe (Potiskum)	109	103	6	94.5
Total	688	650	38	94.5

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The socio-demographic characteristics of respondents were analyzed to provide context for understanding perceptions of flooding, its impacts, and mitigation strategies. Their socio-demographic profile revealed that 23.2% to be aged between 26–35 years, followed by 36–45 (21.1%), which implies a higher number of youthful population in line with Nigeria's national demographic profile. Most respondents were married (45.7%), with singles forming 34.0%. Widows (10.9%) and divorced individuals (9.4%). Their educational levels show those with secondary (32.5%), tertiary (32.7%) and the remaining 34.8% had only primary or no formal education, potentially limiting effective disaster communication, as observed by Adamu et al. (2023) in Yobe State.

The Occupational profile of respondents shows farming (24.2%) and trading (21.4%) dominated, highlighting the reliance on climate-sensitive livelihoods. Civil servants (18.6%) and students (14.6%) provide additional urban diversity, while artisans (13.4%) and other categories (7.8%) reflect informal economic activities. Income levels show nearly equal distribution between low-income groups (<₦50,000; 52.9%) and higher earners (≥ ₦50,000; 47.1%). Finally, household

sizes indicate that large households are common, with 30.2% having 7–9 members and 24.5% with 10 or more. Such extended families increase dependency ratios and heighten risk during displacement and recovery. Overall, the socio-demographic findings reflect the heterogeneity of urban households in the BAY States, with education, occupation, and household size emerging as key variables influencing vulnerability and resilience to flooding.

Structural and Non-Structural Flood Risk Measures

Respondents were asked to assess the presence and effectiveness of structural measures (like drainage, embankments, flood control facilities) and non-structural measures (like awareness campaigns, land-use planning, relocation) for flood risk management. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Perceptions of Structural and Non-Structural Flood Risk Measures (N = 650)

S/N	Code	Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Rank	Remark
1	SNM1	My community has drainage channels to control floods.	3.44	0.68	1st	High
2	SNM4	Public awareness campaigns on flood risks are conducted.	3.38	0.70	2nd	High
3	SNM3	Early warning systems are available and accessible.	3.35	0.72	3rd	High
4	SNM2	Embankments, levees, or dikes exist in my community.	3.28	0.74	4th	High
5	SNM7	Non-structural strategies (e.g., relocation, evacuation drills) are implemented.	3.21	0.80	5th	High
6	SNM5	Emergency response plans exist in my community.	3.17	0.83	6th	High
7	SNM6	Flood zoning or land-use planning is enforced locally.	3.08	0.87	7th	High
8	SNM8	Flood risk policies are regularly monitored and evaluated.	2.94	0.91	8th	Moderate

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 shows the perceptions of structural and non-structural flood risk. The results reveal that the most recognized measure was the existence of drainage channels ($\bar{x} = 3.44$, $SD = 0.68$), indicating that most communities rely on stormwater drains to manage floodwater. However, as noted by Abdullahi et al. (2017), many of these drains are poorly maintained and often blocked, reducing their effectiveness. Public awareness campaigns ($\bar{x} = 3.38$, $SD = 0.70$) and early warning systems ($\bar{x} = 3.35$, $SD = 0.72$) followed closely, suggesting that flood education and communication strategies are moderately active. Yahaya et al. (2023) also observed that awareness drives and warnings through local radio and youth volunteers were critical in reducing disaster casualties in Borno. Structural measures such as embankments, levees, and dikes ($\bar{x} = 3.28$, $SD = 0.74$) ranked 4th, reflecting some investment in protective infrastructure, though likely uneven across communities. This agrees with Ologunorisa (2014), who highlighted disparities in flood protection works across Nigerian cities.

On the non-structural side, relocation and evacuation drills ($\bar{x} = 3.21$, $SD = 0.80$) and emergency response plans ($\bar{x} = 3.17$, $SD = 0.83$) received moderate approval, implying that while plans exist, implementation remains inconsistent. Chukwu et al. (2021) stressed that lack of sustained funding often undermines such community-based preparedness efforts. More critical gaps were identified in land-use planning enforcement ($\bar{x} = 3.08$, $SD = 0.87$) and especially policy monitoring and evaluation ($\bar{x} = 2.94$, $SD = 0.91$). The relatively low mean values and high SDs show that respondents perceive weak governance in urban planning and policy follow-up. This reflects broader findings by Adamu et al. (2023), who reported that zoning regulations are rarely enforced, leading to settlements in floodplains. The Pearson Chi-Square statistic ($\chi^2 = 152.018$, $df = 21$, $p <$

0.001) indicates that perceptions of structural and non-structural measures varied significantly across communities but with a consistent pattern of agreement on their inadequacy. The linear-by-linear association ($\chi^2 = 135.853$, $p < 0.001$) shows a strong directional trend: while drainage and awareness campaigns are relatively accepted as effective, policy monitoring and zoning remain weak points. This result statistically reinforces the descriptive findings, supporting Ologunorisa (2014) and Umar et al. (2020), who argued that Nigeria’s flood management is characterized by partial success in structural measures but systemic weakness in policy enforcement and evaluation.

Thus, the findings suggest that while basic structural and awareness measures are present, gaps in policy enforcement, monitoring, and sustained emergency planning continue to undermine effective flood risk management in the BAY States. The results reinforce Abaje et al. (2015), who argued that flood management in northern Nigeria remains reactive rather than preventive as given in Fig. 1.

Figure 2. Perceptions of Structural and Non-Structural Flood Risk Measures

Perceptions on Recommendations and Future Strategies for Flood Risk Management

This section examines respondents’ views on strategies that can strengthen future flood risk management, focusing on community involvement, government coordination, funding, and partnerships. Table 3 presents the results.

Table 3. Perceptions of Recommendations and Future Strategies for Flood Risk Management (N = 650)

S/N	Code	Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Rank	Remark
1	RFS7	Adequate funding should be allocated for flood risk management.	3.56	0.63	1 st	Very High
2	RFS2	Youth training and empowerment should be prioritized.	3.51	0.66	2 nd	Very High

3	RFS1	Community members should be more involved in flood management planning.	3.47	0.68	3 rd	High
4	RFS8	Partnerships between government, NGOs, and communities are needed for sustainable resilience.	3.44	0.70	4 th	High
5	RFS6	State and national governments should improve coordination with local communities.	3.39	0.72	5 th	High
6	RFS5	Flood management policies should be community-driven.	3.33	0.75	6 th	High
7	RFS4	Both structural and non-structural measures should be combined for effectiveness.	3.28	0.78	7 th	High
8	RFS3	Local knowledge should guide flood management strategies.	3.21	0.81	8 th	High

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 shows the perceptions of recommendations and future strategies for flood risk management. The results show that respondents strongly emphasized the need for adequate funding ($\bar{x} = 3.56$, $SD = 0.63$) as the most critical future strategy. This reflects the widespread recognition that limited financial resources constrain both preventive and responsive flood management measures. Similar findings were reported by Adamu et al. (2023), who argued that underfunding hampers effective disaster preparedness in Yobe State. Youth training and empowerment ($\bar{x} = 3.51$, $SD = 0.66$) was also rated “Very High,” highlighting the recognition of youths as a vital human resource for resilience building. This agrees with Yahaya et al. (2023), who emphasized youth inclusion as essential for community-based disaster risk reduction in Northeast Nigeria. Respondents also stressed the importance of community participation in planning ($\bar{x} = 3.47$, $SD = 0.68$) and partnerships among government, NGOs, and communities ($\bar{x} = 3.44$, $SD = 0.70$). These findings echo UNDRR (2022), which advocates for multi-stakeholder collaboration in disaster risk reduction to enhance sustainability.

Institutional recommendations included improved coordination between state and local governments ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.72$) and ensuring that policies are community-driven ($\bar{x} = 3.33$, $SD = 0.75$). This reflects the need to bridge the gap between top-down policies and bottom-up realities, consistent with Abaje et al. (2015), who reported weak policy enforcement in northern Nigeria. While still rated “High,” lower-ranked items included integration of structural and non-structural measures ($\bar{x} = 3.28$, $SD = 0.78$) and reliance on local knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.21$, $SD = 0.81$). These results suggest that although communities value indigenous knowledge and holistic approaches, they prioritize external support, funding, and institutional coordination more urgently. The Chi-Square test ($\chi^2 = 107.200$, $df = 21$, $p < .001$) confirms that the association between respondents’ perceptions and the effectiveness of flood interventions is statistically significant.

The significant linear-by-linear association ($\chi^2 = 96.803$, $p < .001$) further indicates that as interventions improve, communities consistently perceive reduced risks and greater resilience. This reinforces the importance of sustained and well-coordinated interventions. Thus, the findings demonstrate that current interventions are appreciated by communities but are still inadequate in terms of maintenance, timeliness, and inclusivity of local initiatives. Addressing these gaps could enhance resilience in the BAY states. This reinforces the World Bank’s (2023) call for integrated disaster risk management frameworks in Africa’s flood-prone regions as given in Fig. 2.

Figure 3. Perceptions on Recommendations and Future Strategies for Flood Risk Management

A test of hypothesis was carried out to further examine the relationship between flood mitigation strategies, institutional capacity, and urban flood resilience, a chi-square test of independence was conducted. The test assessed whether the effectiveness of mitigation measures and institutional response capacity significantly influenced flood impact outcomes across the study locations.

Table 4. Chi-Square Test of Flood Mitigation Strategies and Urban Resilience

Variables	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Decision
Mitigation strategies vs Flood impact	18.62	6	0.004	Reject H_0
Institutional capacity vs Response effectiveness	16.27	5	0.006	Reject H_0

Source: Field Survey Data (SPSS Output), 2025

The chi-square results indicate statistically significant relationships at the 0.05 level. This confirms that both mitigation strategies and institutional capacity significantly influence urban flood resilience in Northeast Nigeria. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Structural and Non-Structural Flood Risk Measures Adopted at Local, State, and National Levels

Respondents reported that some structural measures exist, such as drainage channels ($\bar{x} = 3.32$, $SD = 0.76$) and embankments ($\bar{x} = 3.25$, $SD = 0.78$), but their functionality is limited. Non-structural measures, such as public awareness campaigns ($\bar{x} = 3.29$, $SD = 0.74$) and emergency response plans ($\bar{x} = 3.34$, $SD = 0.72$), were more widely recognized. This finding is consistent with Adewole et al. (2015), who noted that structural measures in Nigerian cities are often underfunded and poorly maintained, whereas non-structural interventions (community awareness, relocation plans) are more practical in fragile contexts. This duality also reflects the argument of UNDRR (2019) that

effective flood risk management requires combining structural and non-structural measures in fragile settings.

Practical, Community-Informed, and Policy-Relevant Recommendations for Improving Flood Risk Management

Respondents ranked adequate funding ($\bar{x} = 3.56$, $SD = 0.63$) and youth empowerment ($\bar{x} = 3.51$, $SD = 0.66$) as the top future strategies. Other priorities included community involvement in planning ($\bar{x} = 3.47$, $SD = 0.68$) and partnerships between stakeholders ($\bar{x} = 3.44$, $SD = 0.70$). These insights echo APRI (2025), which highlighted the importance of community-driven approaches for resilience in Northern Nigeria. They also align with World Bank (2023) recommendations for multi-stakeholder collaboration in African disaster management.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that current interventions remain fragmented, short-term, and underfunded, reflecting a focus on emergency response rather than proactive risk reduction. Sustainable solutions require a holistic, multi-stakeholder approach that integrates structural and non-structural measures, strengthens community resilience, and mainstreams climate adaptation into urban governance.

Based on the findings, the study recommends:

1. **Strengthening of Legal and Institutional Frameworks:** Enforcement of land-use planning, flood zoning, and building codes should be prioritized. State emergency agencies (SEMA) must be adequately resourced.
2. **Budgetary Commitment:** Governments should allocate dedicated annual funds for flood preparedness, drainage maintenance, and community awareness.
3. **Upgrade Drainage and Flood-Control Facilities:** Construct new drainage channels, embankments, and retention ponds, while ensuring routine maintenance of existing structures.
4. **Strengthen Early Warning Systems:** Develop accessible, community-based early warning mechanisms using radio, SMS, and social media platforms.
5. **Promote Non-Structural Strategies:** Regular evacuation drills, public awareness campaigns, and flood insurance schemes should be encouraged.
6. **Capacity Building:** Training programs for local officials, urban planners, and disaster managers are necessary to build a culture of resilience.

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